

Jagannath Temple of Puri, Odisha (Orissa), India

By Aaron Michael Ullrey, University of Houston, University of Naropa

Entry tags: Hinduism, indic religion, Vaishnavism, Polytheistic, Shaivism, Indic Religious Traditions, Religious Place, Religious Group, Religious Complex, Regional Religious System, Bhakti, Tantra, India

Jagannath means "Lord of the World", from which the British derived the word juggernaut describing an out of control truck, and he is the most prominent deity in Odisha, with his most important temple in the beach-side town of Puri. Jagannath is worshipped in the form of three (sometimes four) large wooden duties, and his main images are brought out of his temple once a year, placed upon large ornate chariots, worshipped variously, and then the chariots are pulled through the streets so that the deity(deities) might "vacation", residing in a nearby temple to Gundicha, a goddess, and this temple is known as his "summer home" or his "garden home" where Jagannath lives for nine days every year. This procession of the god is called his rath yatra "chariot pilgrimage". Jagannath is a sort of trinity formed from the Lord himself, his brother Balabhadra, and his sister Subhadra, sometimes accompanied by a smaller image called Sudarshana. These roughly correspond to mythical figures associated with Krishna. That said, scholars have established that this cult likely started with a single Shaiva deities (maybe an Ekapada Bhairava), then that deity became Narasimha (the man-lion) and he was paired with his wife Laksmi, over time this admittedly tantric pair that is widely worshipped in South East Central India was made into a Vaishnava, the Lord of the World, though even the final element, Natha, suggest Shaivism. Jagannath was then associated with Krishna, Laksmi was turned into Subadra, and a third figure Balabadra was added to create family scene. The fourth figure Sudarshana may connect to Krishnas weapon. In this way the local regional god Jagannatha was steadily shifted from a tribal and Shaiva orientation to a wider, even trans local Vaishnava orientation. Though Bhakta worshippers may argue that Jagannath is Krishna or an incarnation of Vishnu, the people of Orissa see Jagannath as an independent and majestic deity. I translate a common phrase there, "We are all safe/prosperous in Jagannath's kingdom". Jagannath is seen to pervade the town and the region. The Rath Yatra is a huge yearly event, setting records each year for pilgrims and spiritual/religious tourists that cause the relatively small city's population to swell, recent years have had over one million (10 lakhs) of visitors. Notably, the city has a huge road from the main temple to the Gundicha temple, and this road is the path on which the chariots are pulled. When the rath yatra is not in session, these wide roads are mostly empty, and most of the rest of the city roads stretch from this main "road", which is the size of a small airport. The Jagannath temple itself is the most prominent building in the town. The temple complex has extensive structures in addition to the main temple to the deities. The temple has a twenty foot wall around the complex, and entrance is barred for non-hinds. The only time non-hinduss can see deities is the rath yatra. The temple processes a wide range of worship offerings throughout the day, and the remains from these offerings are distributed as prasad. The deity Jagannath and his triad are not limited to this main temple but can be found throughout India, especially where folks from Orissa have settled. Various temples in the United States display small-scale versions of the trinity, and many of them perform a truncated rath yatra around the temple spaces yearly.

Date Range: 1200 CE - 2018 CE
 Region: Odisha
 Region tags: Asia, South Asia, India, Odisha
 Contemporary Odisha, a state in Eastern India.

Status of Participants:

- Elite
- Religious Specialists
- Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

— Body of water (as distinct from source)

Notes: Associated with the ocean and beach. Considered a sacred grove or dharm.

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

— Yes

A single structure

— No

One single feature

— Purposefully placed plants

A group of structures:

— Yes

Notes: Many temples, major to the three images and minor to other deities.

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No

Notes: The temples have evolved over time in the complex.

- ↳ A group of features:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - Yes

Notes: The complex is vast. And it has major and minor temples. That said, the whole town of puri can be considered an extension of the temple.

- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
 - Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
 - Worship

- ↳ Worship:
 - Communal

Notes: Priest perform communal worship. Each individual person attending the temple has their own ritual moment of seeing the deity.

- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes

Notes: The temple is for the most part stable, though small sections of the complex may change. That said, the images are made of wood and they are periodically deconsecrated and renewed with newly crafted wood images.

- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes

Notes: All polytheistic temple evolve in South Asia. Moreover the deities have shifted identity over time, from tribal, to shaiva, to vaishnav.

- ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - No

- ↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
 - Yes

- ↳ In antiquity
 - Periodically

Notes: The site was likely always a temple of some form, but its current form is established in 12th century.

- ↳ In modernity
 - Renaissance
 - Post-Renaissance

Notes: The temple has evolved, walls are built and changed, man-as expanded and restored periodically.

- Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
 - Yes

- ↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
 - Yes [specify]: Jagannath

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

— Yes [specify]: Jagannath, Subhadra, Balabadhra

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Kulke Hermann. 1993. Kings and Cults : State Formation and Legitimation in India and Southeast Asia. New Delhi: Manohar Publishers & Distributors.
- Source 2: Kulke Hermann and Burkhard Schnepel. 2001. Jagannath Revisited : Studying Society Religion and the State in Orissa. New Delhi: Manohar.
- Source 3: Sontheimer Gunther-Dietz and Hermann Kulke. 2001. Hinduism Reconsidered Paperback ed. New Delhi: Manohar.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

— Yes

↳ Type of feature

— Clearing

Notes: There is a large complex with gardens and groves. Also, to some degree the road for the Rath Yatra should be considered a part of the site.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

— No

Notes: There is a history of Saints here, especially the saint Caitanya.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.shreejagannatha.in>
- Source 1 Description: Official Temple Website
- Source 2 URL: https://dsal.uchicago.edu/cgi-bin/aiis/aiis_query.py?start_hit=1&keyword=Jagannatha&location=&date=
- Source 2 Description: American Institute of India Studies image gallery, specific to Jagannath at Puri
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.google.com/search?client=safari&rls=en&tbm=vid&sxsrf=AB5stBg9g5gilIiBaSMmxZmRVqXCHk1NQq:1689104088571&q=jagannath+puri+yatra+2022&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEwjl>
- Source 3 Description: 2022 Rath Yatra coverage

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

— No

Notes: There is a history of kings associated here, but they are not worshipped. Current king figures are important in the annual rath yatra rituals.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

— No

Notes: There has been a bit of speculative excavation but the temple is an active site.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

— Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

— Yes

Notes: Walls split the main temple from the rest of the city. That said there are other Jagannath temples, much smaller, that are integrated into the urban environment.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

— No

Notes: This has long been occupied, since at least the 12th century.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

— Yes

- ↳ Specify
 - King or emperor

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

- No
 - Notes: Non religious sites and homes are found right up to the streets around the main walls.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

- Yes
 - ↳ Groups:
 - Priests
 - Specialized labourers/craftspeople
 - Notes: Priests oversee the maintenance and building. But a specific ethnic group of craftsmen build the chariots every year and periodically re-build the wooden images.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

- Yes
 - ↳ Specify
 - Revealed by high god
 - Notes: Varied stories describe the temple complex and city founded by varied gods, literary figures, and saintly seers.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

- Yes
 - Notes: Birthplace is tricky, but you could argue this is the birth of Jagannath.

Was the place created as the result of an event:

- Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

- Yes
 - ↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Varied kings and emperors over the year would sponsor Jagannath and associate with him. Jagannath is a perfect ruler, so also must be the king who is associated with him.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

- Expectation of favor in return
 - Notes: Hindu temples are transactional. Gods are worshipped out of pure reverence, but all worship is also an exchange relationship. Kings would patronize the temple and the god would grant them power, prestige, and legitimacy.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

- No
 - Notes: There are manuscript archives around, and hindu temples often have scripture repositories.

Sources and Excavations

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– Source 3 URL: <https://www.google.com/search?client=safari&rls=en&tbm=vid&sxsrf=AB5stBg9g5gillIiBaSMmxZmRVqXCHK1NQQ:1689104088571&q=jagannath+puri+yatra+2022&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEv>

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Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

Notes: Associated with the ocean and beach. Considered a sacred grove or dham.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

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Notes: This has long been occupied, since at least the 12th century.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: Non religious sites and homes are found right up to the streets around the main walls.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

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↳ A group of structures:

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↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

Notes: The site was likely always a temple of some form, but its current form is established in 12th century.

↳ In modernity

– Renaissance

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: The temple has evolved, walls are built and changed, mandapa expanded and restored periodically.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Jagannath

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Jagannath, Subhadra, Balabadhra

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Notes: There is a history of Saints here, especially the saint Caitanya.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: There is a history of kings associated here, but they are not worshipped. Current king figures are important in the annual rath yatra rituals.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Priests

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Notes: Priests oversee the maintenance and building. But a specific ethnic group of craftsmen build the chariots every year and periodically re-build the wooden images.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Revealed by high god

Notes: Varied stories describe the temple complex and city founded by varied gods, literary figures, and saintly seers.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

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Notes: Varied kings and emperors over the year would sponsor Jagannath and associate with him. Jagannath is a perfect ruler, so also must be the king who is associated with him.

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– Expectation of favor in return

Notes: Hindu temples are transactional. Gods are worshipped out of pure reverence, but all worship is also an exchange relationship. Kings would patronize the temple and the god would grant them power, prestige, and legitimacy.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: There are manuscript archives around, and hindu temples often have scripture repositories.

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Notes: There are quite a number of decoration features. Also, there are varied offerings of decoration that are more or less temporary.

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Jagannath, Balabhadra, and Subadhra are depicted all over the place. But the three main, large deities are found in the major mandala.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Various saints, especially Caitanya are worshipped throughout the temple area.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– I don't know

Notes: There could be murals inside.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– I don't know

Notes: Yoginis.....animal headed wisdom beings/witches are common in this area, but I have not seen them in or around the temple.

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

Notes: All these elements are found variously, which is common in Hindu temples.

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

Notes: The deities and the temple complex cannot be accessed by non-Hindus. That said, once a year the deities emerge from the temple in order to be pulled through the town on 45 foot high chariots.

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

Notes: Three major images revealing circular wooden deities and a fourth pillar deity. They are made of wood. They are worshipped all together, though Jagannatha could be considered independent. Smaller temples depict the other deities, but they are all mostly found in a group of three (or four).

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– I don't know

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– I don't know

↳ Are there paintings present:

– I don't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– I don't know

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– I don't know

↳ Other type of decoration:

– I don't know

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Temple associated with ocean. Temple complex is thought to be a sacred grove or dham.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: Some temples are close together and some are connected, all connect in the larger temple complex behind the walls.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The main temples to the deities are the most prominent.

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

Notes: The eyes in general are particular. Jagannath has distinctively shaped, more rounded eyes, and the other deities have more almond eyes.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

Notes: Balabhadra is sometimes associated with snake imagery.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

Notes: The deities are human like but they are stylized. They theoretically have legs and heads and eyes, but they are not really human.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Yes

Notes: The deities are distinct. They are rounded globes with peg-like arms. They are painted with otherworldly eyes and features.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– No

Notes: Around the temple there are some paintings of human saints.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– I don't know

Notes: I am not sure if there are specific depictions in the temple, but there are a wide range of supernatural tales and mahatmyas in the literature pamphlets from the temple and around the city.

↳ Human narratives

– No

Notes: Some depictions of varied important kingly patrons.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Notes: the temple is quite grand, but I am not sure if monumental applies. It is one of the main pilgrimage sites in Hinduism.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Specific trees in specific areas are used to create and recreate the icons.

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

Notes: The buildings and walls are made of stone and concrete.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: The images are made of wood, but they are very specifically crafted by an ethnic group of craftsmen.

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

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- ↳ Are there mosaics present:
 - I don't know
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 - I don't know
- ↳ Other type of decoration:
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Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

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 - Yes
 - Notes: The eyes in general are particular. Jagannath has distinctively shaped, more rounded eyes, and the other deities have more almond eyes.
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Notes: Some depictions of varied important kingly patrons.

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

– No

↳ Offerings of food:

– Yes [specify]: Fruits, flowers, and the like

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– No

↳ Human sacrifice:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Sacred objects:

– Yes [specify]: In a way the chariots themselves and the ropes to pull them are sacred offerings.

↳ Daily life objects:

– Yes [specify]: Everyday foodstuffs are often offered. Also oils.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: As with all Hinduism the rituals in temple must be performed perfectly by practitioners in a state of purity.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: The deities expect transitions and rituals, though I am not sure anyone would ever NOT want to perform them. There is a lot of joy in the festivals and rituals.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

Notes: Supposedly Jagannath cares about no non-Hindus. Also, this is the home of the god, and he expects it to be maintained as such.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

- ↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
 - optional (common)
 - Notes: This is considered by modern Hindus to be one of the four great pilgrimages in India, especially to the Rath Yatra. That said, there are more formal pilgrimages by modern groups like ISKON. Also, regional members may have more rigorous pilgrimages.
- ↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:
 - Yes
 - Notes: This was always a regional temple where folk would come from far off. The pilgrimage dually had the effect of legitimizing and glorifying the patronizing kings.
- ↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
 - No
- ↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
 - Yes
- ↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The Gunjdicha temple where Jagannath stays in his summer home temple is empty except when he is there. Also there is a huge road which is the route for the Rath Yatra.

Is divination present:

– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

- ↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The largest scale ritual is the Rath Yatra which takes place of many days and is surrounded by rituals for weeks.
- ↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Extensive daily worship rituals are found in the main temples, and some priest do work in smaller temples. Also, individuals will perform small rituals throughout the temple space.
- ↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
 - specify: 1,000,000 in 2022 at the Rath Yatra. Many many daily visitors to the temple year round.
- ↳ How often do these rituals take place:
 - specify: Rath Yatra once a year.
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Brahmin ritual experts consult throughout.
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Brahmin ritual experts consult throughout.
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - No
 - Notes: This is a remarkably hindu event, but I would argue there are a wide range of tribal practices integrated into the worship of Jagannath.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Notes: Not during the rituals officially. However, cannabis is very common throughout Puri, and there are even bhang shops associated with the region and temple.

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Jagannath is considered a high god, a regional god, a member of a trinity, an incarnation of Vishnu.....all of the above at any time.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: They pray. And the act of darshan is a communication.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Notes: Not formally, but some folk will claim they were healed through the grace of this god and attending the pilgrimage.

Are previously human spirits present:

– I don't know

Notes: Any sacred place in this area is thought to also be inhabited by perfected beings and seers.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Yearly Rath Yatra

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

Notes: All members of the community and all visitors of any religion or class are welcome at the Rath Yatra.

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

↳ Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The temple space is always maintained, but there are special rituals like the king sweeping the chariots for the Rath Yatra.

↳ Requires new construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

Notes: In the pilgrimage the chariots are built fresh every year and they are decorated variously including wooden carvings of deities and mythological motifs.

↳ Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):

– Yes

Notes: Periodic repair and replacement of wooden figures.

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: As of 2022....over a million attended.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Notes: Category of feasting is hard to apply.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: At the edges of the city and in beach areas are cremation sites that have an association with Jagannath.

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to the elements:

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– I don't know

Notes: Hard to say. People do often bring physical offerings, and it would be rude to the god not to bring something or make a money offering.

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– I don't know

Notes: Some bring incredibly valuable offerings to patronize the god, other folks bring simple offerings.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:
– Yes
Notes: Some extravagant offerings, but mostly the offerings are flowers and fruits.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):
– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– I don't know
Notes: It is not required....but it seems mandatory.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:
– No
Notes: They can be seen as the images. The images are the very real bodies of the deities.

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:
– I don't know
Notes: A spirit of emotion and devotion pervades.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:
– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):
– Yes
Notes: The temple complex is as complicated as a city with a full staff.

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:
– Yes
Notes: The wooden images are periodically removed, deconsecrated, and a secret item is removed from their center. Then newly crafted wooden images are consecrated, have the secret item installed, and then are installed in the temple.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
– Yes
Notes: There are permanent maintenance staff and temple priests to perform ritual services. Also, the construction of the chariots and periodic new images belong to a specific lineage of craftsmen.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

Notes: All hindus can see the images.

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– Yes

Notes: Non-hindus are barred from the main temple. However, any person in Puri can see the images during the annual Rath Yatra.

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: At the edges of the city and in beach areas are cremation sites that have an association with Jagannath.

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to the elements:

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Jagannath is considered a high god, a regional god, a member of a trinity, an incarnation of Vishnu.....all of the above at any time.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

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Notes: Any sacred place in this area is thought to also be inhabited by perfected beings and seers.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

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Notes: All hindus can see the images.

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– Yes

Notes: Non-hindus are barred from the main temple. However, any person in Puri can see the images during the annual Rath Yatra.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Libations:
 - No
 - ↳ Offerings of food:
 - Yes [specify]: Fruits, flowers, and the like
 - ↳ Animal sacrifice:
 - No
 - ↳ Human sacrifice:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Sacred objects:
 - Yes [specify]: In a way the chariots themselves and the ropes to pull them are sacred offerings.
 - ↳ Daily life objects:
 - Yes [specify]: Everyday foodstuffs are often offered. Also oils.
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
 - Notes: As with all Hinduism the rituals in temple must be performed perfectly by practitioners in a state of purity.
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:
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 - Notes: The deities expect transitions and rituals, though I am not sure anyone would ever NOT want to perform them. There is a lot of joy in the festivals and rituals.
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:
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 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:
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- Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:
- Yes
 - ↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:
 - Yes
 - Notes: They pray. And the act of darshan is a communication.
 - ↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:
 - I don't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: The largest scale ritual is the Rath Yatra which takes place of many days and is surrounded by rituals for weeks.

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Notes: Extensive daily worship rituals are found in the main temples, and some priest do work in smaller temples. Also, individuals will perform small rituals throughout the temple space.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

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↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: Brahmin ritual experts consult throughout.

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↳ Are there synchronic practices:

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↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Notes: Not during the rituals officially. However, cannabis is very common throughout Puri, and there are even bhang shops associated with he region and temple.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– I don't know

Notes: Hard to say. People do often bring physical offerings, and it would be rude to the god not to bring something or make a money offering.

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– Yes
Notes: There are permanent maintenance staff and temple priests to perform ritual services. Also, the construction of the chariots and periodic new images belong to a specific lineage of craftsmen.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:
– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
– optional (common)
Notes: This is considered by modern Hindus to be one of the four great pilgrimages in India, especially to the Rath Yatra. That said, there are more formal pilgrimages by modern groups like ISKON. Also, regional members may have more rigorous pilgrimages.

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Is this place a venue for feasting:
– No

Are festivals present:
– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

—specify: Yearly Rath Yatra

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

—All members

Notes: All members of the community and all visitors of any religion or class are welcome at the Rath Yatra.

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Notes: In the pilgrimage the chariots are built fresh every year and they are decorated variously including wooden carvings of deities and mythological motifs.

↳ Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):

— Yes

Notes: Periodic repair and replacement of wooden figures.

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

—number: As of 2022.....over a million attended.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

— No

Notes: Category of feasting is hard to apply.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

— No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

— No

Notes: Not formally, but some folk will claim they were healed through the grace of this god and attending the pilgrimage.

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

— Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

— Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

— No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

— No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with

subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time
– Yes

↳ Present part time
– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
– Yes
Notes: Entirely male. That said, there is a loose tradition of devadasis....these are courtesans that are married to god, married here to Jagannath.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
– Yes
Notes: Ethnicity is tricky. The specialists are generally brahmins. Craftsmen of a specific subcaste. The majority of folk working and dwelling near the temple are Oriya ethnicity.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
– Yes
Notes: Brahmin priests. And a specific subcaste of craftsmen.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
– I don't know
Notes: Some are associated for life. Not all.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:
– Yes
Notes: Brahmins are the most pure of the caste groups. There are non-brahmin craftsman people who create and maintain the important wood work for the temple and the festival.

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:
– Yes
Notes: Food distribution of prasad from ritual, also there is a large kitchen for serving Hindus.

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):
– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):
– No

↳ Function for water management:
– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:
– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:
– Yes

Notes: There are many mahatmyas (texts that glorify a place and its deities) that are associated with Jagannath and Puri. Jagannath can be found referenced and puri as a holy place in varied Epics and Puranas.

↳ Are they written at this place:
– Yes

↳ Are they oral:
– Yes
Notes: There are some oral praise bhajana and songs.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:
– Yes
Notes: The stories are wide from established by a vedic seer to a king finding a special post in a holy river and then making that post into the first Jagannath image.

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:
– Yes
Notes: Brahmins will interpret the scriptures, but, however, their expertise is not in wisdom or lore but knowledge of rituals and maintaining purity.

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:
– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:
– Yes
Notes: There are some living quarters for the full time priests.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):
– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:
– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:
– Yes
Notes: In the past there were villages that would give taxes to the temple because the temple sorta owned the villages.

↳ Does this place lease out tools:
– I don't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:
– Yes
Notes: Training in ritual and liturgy for brahmin priests in training.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:
Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders
– Yes

Notes: There is a temple and a temple board, there are brahmin groups and families associated with the temple, there is a full staff for the temple, there are also security forces.

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

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↳ Present full time
– Yes

- ↳ Present part time
 - Yes
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Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

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- ↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

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Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

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↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

Notes: Food distribution of prasad from ritual, also there is a large kitchen for serving Hindus.

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: There are many mahatmyas (texts that glorify a place and its deities) that are associated with Jagannath and Puri. Jagannath can be found referenced and puri as a holy place in varied Epics and Puranas.

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Bibliography

General References

Reference: Jagannath Temple of Puri, Odisha (Orissa), India, Kramrisch, Stella. *The Hindu Temple* (vol. 1 and 2). Vol. 5. Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass Publ., 2002.